

Popular Article

A review on African swine fever disease and its control

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Abstract

African Swine Fever (ASF) is a highly contagious, fatal disease of domestic as well as wild boar transmitted through direct and indirect contacts, ingestion of contaminated feedstuffs and by biting of tick vectors. The disease does not infect humans (nonzoonotic) and any other livestock species. ASF was first detected in 1921 in Kenya and is generally prevalent and endemic in countries of sub-Saharan Africa, Europe and in some Caribbean countries. In India first outbreak of ASF was notified in January 2020 in the North Eastern States of Assam and Arunachal Pradesh. Due to the rapid spreading nature of the disease ASF Virus crosses the boundary and subsequently diseases have been also reported in different states of the country. This is the first time that ASF has been reported in India and hence all precautionary and emergency initiatives should be taken towards rapid containment of the disease with focus towards control and eradication within shortest possible period of time to avoid spread of the disease.

Introduction

African Swine Fever (ASF) is a highly infectious and contagious hemorrhagic viral disease of domestic/captive and feral/wild boar. All breeds, and all ages of pig species are affected. Mortality rate of ASF disease is 100%. No other livestock species are affected with ASF. ASF does not infect human (nonzoonotic) or other livestock species. Hence, it is not a public health risk. Due to the absence of vaccines with protective efficacy, ASF represents a serious threat to European countries and especially developing country like India.

Etiology

The causative agent of ASF belongs to genus *Asfavirus* of the family *Asfaviridae*. ASFV is enveloped Ds DNA virus is the only virus listed in the genus. . The virus can persist for up to a month in contaminated pig pens and pork products for over 4-1/2 months. The virus can transmit the disease through blood tissue, secretions and excretions of sick and dead animals. Disease can be transmitted by various modes such as direct transmission via contact with sick and healthy animals and indirect via by feeding of garbage containing ASF infected meat (uncooked pork products remain infectious for 3-6 months), fomites like premises, vehicles, equipments and clothes. Disease may spread through soft tick of genus *Ornithodoros* and acts as a biological vector.

Symptoms

Clinical symptoms of ASF varies according to different factors such as virulence of virus, route of exposure of disease, infectious dose, breed of swine affected and endemic status in the area. Clinical symptoms are divided into four forms. Incubation period in natural infection of disease varies from 4-19 days.

- Per-Acute form: In this form swine's having high fever (41-42⁰c) and sudden death within 1-3 days of infection.
- Acute form: In this form of disease swine having high fever (40-42⁰c) with reddening of the whole skin but mostly seen at skin of ear tip, tail, ventral aspects of chest and abdomen, and death of animal within 6-9 days (for highly virulent strain) and 11-15 days (for moderately virulent strain). Mortality rates up to 90-100%.
- Sub-Acute form: In this form swine showing slight fever, reddening of skin and death occur within 15-45 days. Mortality rates up to 30-70%.
- Chronic form: Pig shows irregular peaks of temperature, respiratory sings, necrosis in skin, ulcer, arthritis and joint swelling. Mortality rate less than 30%.

Diagnosis

Confirmatory diagnosis of disease has been done by identification and isolation of virus, detection of antigen in smears/section of tissue using fluorescent antibody test (FAT) and by PCR/real-time PCR. Serological test like ELISA, IFAT, IPT and Immunoblotting (IBT) are also used. Differential Diagnosis

from CSF and other related disease, the most important differential diagnosis of ASF is CSF also known as hog cholera, which is caused by *Pestivirus* in the Flaviviridae family. It is only way to distinguish between them by confirmatory laboratory diagnosis.

Prevention and Control

Prevention is the only measure as there is no effective vaccine for the disease. Since there is no vaccine available, reliable and early diagnosis of disease is essential for the implementation of strict sanitary and biosecurity control measures to prevent the spread of disease.

- Any suspected case/pathogenic gross lesions and clinical signs in dead and affected pigs, immediate isolation and restriction of movement should be followed.
- After declaration of disease epicenter and surveillance zone should be identified and immediate sealing and disinfection of affected animal shed and premises.
- The dead pigs should be disposed of by deep burial/incineration only and not thrown in rivers/canals/streams/water bodies. Carcass will destroy under official veterinary supervision with adopting all biosecurity measures.
- Thorough cleaning of farm/infected area with water and disinfection carried out with 2% sodium hypochlorite/sodium hydroxide or a detergent-based virucidal agent.
- Creating Public awareness among the animal health workers about the disease, trained them for early recognition, collection, and dispatches the suspected clinical samples, and intimation to the nearest dispensary are important steps towards the health care system.
- Area should be specified and demarcated into 3 specified zone Infected Zone (IZ) -1 km radius from epicenter/infected zone, Surveillance zone (SZ) - 10 km radius from infected zone/9 km outside the IZ, Disease free zone/non-infected area (FZ) – area outside the SZ. All pigs within IZ (1km of epicenter) will be humanely culled as soon as possible.
- Pig markets and abattoirs should strictly close and trade of pork meat and meat products is prohibited.
- Post operational protocol (POP) will be operational for 6 months after proper cleaning and disinfection operation. Fumigation once in every 15 days after completion of control operation, and pig is introduced into the area only after next 6 months after issue of Sanitization Certificate.

Reference

- Kabra A, Mukim M, Uddin K, Kabra R, Kukkar R. African Swine Fever: An Emerging Viral Disease in India–A Review. *Journal of Biological and chemical Chronicles*. 2020; 6(1):10-18.
- Juszkiewicz, M., Walczak, M., Mazur-Panasiuk, N. and Wozniakowski, G. (2019). Virucidal effect of chosen disinfectants against African swine fever virus (ASFV) preliminary studies *pol. J. Vet. Sci.*, 22(4): 777-780.
- Kouam, M.K., Jacouba, M. and Moussala, J.O. (2020). Management and biosecurity practices on pig farms in the Western Highlands of Cameroon (Central Africa). *Vet. Med. Sci.*, 6(1): 82-91
- Food and Agriculture Organization. (2010). Good Practices for Biosecurity in the pig Sector Issues and Options in Developing and Transition Countries, FAO Animal Production and Health Paper No. 169. Food and Agriculture Organization, Rome.

